

Green Erasmus Guidelines for Environmental Activities during Mobility Exchange

sustainable behaviours and lifestyles through activities that connect international students and locals

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INTRODUCTION, OBJECTIVE AND TARGET

Introduction

The Erasmus+ Programme is one of the most successful European initiatives, providing great opportunities to study and live abroad for many Europeans. Although generations benefited from it socially and culturally, the natural environment has been negatively affected by the increasing number of Erasmus+ exchanges, predominantly done via air travel. In line with the European Green Deal, the Erasmus+ programme has the environment at its heart and has defined **environmental sustainability as one of its priorities for the 2021-2027 period**.

In this context, the [Green Erasmus project](#) strives to improve the environmental sustainability of the Erasmus+ Programme and raise awareness across the European Higher Education sector about the importance of sustainable internationalisation. Thanks to a **holistic approach** that encompasses the lifecycle and several dimensions of Erasmus+ mobility, the Green Erasmus project results are **conceived to raise awareness and increase literacy about sustainability by providing user-friendly tools** to Higher Education Institutions as well as local, incoming and outgoing students.

Objective and Target

The Green Erasmus guidelines for environmental activities encourage sustainable behaviours and lifestyles through activities that connect international students and locals. Therefore, the aim of the guidelines is also to foster civic engagement and intercultural dialogue.

The guidelines are targeted at local student associations wishing to engage international and local students and work together with local environmental associations to understand the environmental issues, at the global and hosting country level, by using a learning-by-doing approach. The guidelines have been conceived for any kind of student activity organisers: aspiring environmental experts, nature lovers, and those who are not yet familiar with environmental sustainability.

**HOW TO
USE THE
GUIDELINES**

**SHINE
AND INSPIRE**

How to Use the Guidelines

The guidelines are divided into three main areas:

- **Sport & Outdoor;**
- **Awareness & Activism;**
- **Responsible consumption.**

For each of these areas we propose:

- **Events;**
- **Workshops;**
- **Campaigns;**
- **Volunteering on exchange.**

For each activity we indicate:

- a number of environmental objectives to aim for, such as protecting and promoting biodiversity, promoting slow and sustainable travel, fighting climate crisis, fostering a circular economy, etc.;
- learning outcomes, namely what participants and organisers can learn by participating and organising that specific activity;
- the suggested duration of the activity;
- a description of the activity which can be used to create the activity and promote it;
- specific participants to target;
- an external local partner(s) to cooperate with, ensuring participants benefit from the expertise of an environmental association but also engage with the local community and experience cultural exchange;
- environmental considerations to take into account while organising the event;
- extra resources (when available) to find out more;
- concrete event examples to provide inspiration.

Therefore, the guidelines are organised to allow student associations working with and for international students **to browse the table of contents, find the most attractive activity** for them and use the related information to create their own event. The Green Erasmus consortium highly recommends **focusing on the leisure side of the activity whilst stressing its learning outcomes** and taking into account its **environmental aspects and impact**.

Shine and inspire

The Green Erasmus consortium encourages the organisers of environmental activities to report them in the [Activities platform](#) to foster visibility and inspire other student organisations. The platform is powered by the Erasmus Student Network, but any external organisation can [register](#) and use it. The platform is accessible by any user and allows getting a better understanding of the incredible diversity and impact of the activities implemented by the Erasmus Generation. It contains activities focusing on culture, education & youth, environmental sustainability, health & well-being, skills & employability and social inclusion.

When you report your activity, make sure to tick the “Green Erasmus” project tag, and choose the appropriate “objectives” and “types of activities”.

SPORTS AND OUTDOOR

In this section, you can find examples of sports and outdoor activities through which different environmental objectives are addressed, such as protecting nature and promoting biodiversity, fostering a circular economy, promoting slow and sustainable travel, boosting urban nature, reducing waste and promoting recycling, and encouraging wildlife protection.

Events

Bike Tour

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity, promoting slow and sustainable travel.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning

- to travel sustainably during an Erasmus experience;
- the advantages of such travel both for nature and physical and mental health;
- to behave responsibly during a bike tour;
- to detect the natural features of your hosting region/area.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning

- to organise a slow travel trip;
- to manage and guide participants outside of urban areas;
- to establish partnerships with local associations;
- to convey slow travel key messages and benefits for the environment, including local biodiversity.

Time allocation

From five hours to two days.

Description

Bike tours are the best way to discover the surroundings of Erasmus cities and reconnect with nature after busy and hectic times. Whether a half-day ride or a weekend bike tour, cycling slows our pace and enables us to look at the surrounding environment through a new lens and at zero emissions: bicycles hardly produce any pollution (e.g. noise or air pollution) and make us explore the local fauna and flora in detail. Cities might be green, but we can find certain species of plants,

peculiar to that region, only if we leave urban areas. Lastly, we suggest organisers stop at a local restaurant to discover local products. Food is also an expression of a place's biodiversity.

Target group

International students who would like to discover the surroundings or countryside of their Erasmus city, who are in good physical condition for a ride and willing to pedal for the whole duration of the activity.

External collaboration

99% of Erasmus students do not arrive at their Erasmus destination with a bike. Therefore, a rental scheme is necessary for this activity. Some cities now host bike tourism associations that already offer such tours or might want to tailor one with you, or can help you set up one. If there is no such association, contacting a bicycle rental shop is your alternative. Try to negotiate a group price (either for guided or not guided options) and explain your goal of raising awareness about the benefits of slow travel with Erasmus students. They might appreciate the idea and the long-term perspective. Moreover, we suggest you collaborate with local NGOs that promote sustainable travel and, if possible, involve an environmental guide to help the participants discover the local biodiversity.

Environmental considerations

Although bike tourism is slow and environmentally friendly, some behaviours are not.

Do not:

- shout and talk loudly in a natural reserve or protected area (if you end up visiting one for example), it is disruptive;
- abandon the track if you cross a forest to protect the wilderness;
- pick up or feed wild animals.

Do:

- keep the places how you found them and dispose of your waste correctly.

Tips

- To avoid dropouts, set a participation fee to secure participants' registration and participation.
- Check the route and inform the participants of road conditions and slopes.
- This is not an easy activity to organise. Set a maximum number of participants and start from a short tour (possibly in a flat area or just a bit hilly) in the immediate surroundings.
- If you are an expert, combine riding with the use of a train (not all have bike wagons) and stay overnight in a village or a town.
- If the locality allows, combine this activity with a cultural visit.
- Within the bike tour, you could stop in different interesting areas and organise an activity in each one of them (cleaning up, cultural visit, meeting with a local NGO...).

Example

Have a look at [this activity](#) organised by ESN Pisa: they managed to combine the discovery of different green areas with some moments of relaxation at the sea by using sustainable means of transport.

Hike

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity, promoting slow and sustainable travel.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning

- to travel sustainably during an Erasmus experience;
- the advantages of such travel both for nature and physical and mental health;
- to behave responsibly during a hike;
- to detect the natural peculiarities of your hosting region/area.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning

- to organise a slow travel trip;
- to manage and guide participants outside of urban areas;
- to establish partnerships with local associations;
- to convey slow travel key messages and benefits for the environment, including local biodiversity.

Time allocation

From four hours to two days.

Description

Like a bike tour, a hike is the best way to reconnect with nature and discover the surroundings of Erasmus cities. Slow your pace, immerse yourself in a soothing environment, and read about the area you are exploring. Walking allows you to carefully observe the local flora and fauna. To minimise your carbon footprint, choose a trail reachable by public transport and start from a small village or town. This way, you could combine the hike with a short cultural and historical sightseeing. Stop at a local restaurant to support communities and businesses through ecotourism or simply organise a picnic.

Target group

International students who would like to discover the surroundings or countryside of their Erasmus city, who are in good physical condition (criteria might change depending on the difficulty level) and are willing to walk for the whole duration of the activity.

External collaboration

- Many cities have hiking groups or associations that organise day hikes for different difficulty levels. Contact them to organise your hike with their help and guidance or ask to join an already existing hike activity to get to know some locals.
- Some associations are active in the promotion of the cultural heritage of the area, a peculiar flora or fauna specimen, or generally in eco-tourism. Do not forget to contact them and increase the social, cultural, and environmental value of your activity, or simply organise a picnic.

Environmental considerations

Behave responsibly to do an environmentally-friendly hike.

If you want to forage for some herbs or fruit, make sure that there are many specimens in that spot and harvest a small quantity only for personal consumption. This way you make sure they keep reproducing themselves, and you do not take more than you need.

Do not:

- shout and talk loudly in a natural wild area. You might disturb animals;
- abandon the track if you cross a forest to protect the wilderness;
- pick up or feed wild animals.

Do:

- keep the things how you found them and dispose of your waste correctly.

Tips

- Check the trail and inform the participants of trail conditions and slopes; do not pick difficult or height-exposed paths;
- Consider the length and the slope of your hike to calculate the duration of this activity and the public transport connections;
- Do not leave anyone behind. To easily keep track of the group, keep the group small and have one volunteer in the front and back of the group;
- If you want to go pro, organise a hiking weekend and stay overnight in a village or a town; camping might be a great idea if the season allows it;
- If the locality allows, combine this activity with a cultural visit to a town or village on the way. You can also combine the hike with a clean-up activity or with a meeting with a local NGO engaged in the eco-tourism and preservation of the area;
- Consider combining this activity with a light touch of litter pick along the way.

Example

The [wine hike](#) by ESN TU Wien is an example of combining nature and food, environment and culture.

Green Marathon

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity, promoting slow and sustainable travel.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning to

- appreciate participation in group sport activities in nature;
- take part in activities in nature (parks, groves, beaches) during their Erasmus+ mobility;
- be aware of the need for physical exercise.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning how to

- organise a green marathon event in an urban or non-urban environment;
- cooperate with sports/marathon teams within and/or outside the university;
- manage teams in a sports event such as a marathon.

Time allocation

From three hours to one day, depending on how far the destination is.

Description

A Green Marathon (not an actual marathon, but a run of any distance) event gives participants the opportunity to bond with both Erasmus+ and local students, visit green destinations close to the city (such as groves, forests, national parks, and water features), and observe the natural beauty of the place where they are undertaking their Erasmus+. Finally, through this activity, they get into the process of making use of green spaces and start the habit of exercising in them.

Target group

Anyone who is willing to participate in a sports event in nature while on their Erasmus+ mobility.

External collaboration

A Green Marathon activity can be organised with or without collaboration with external partners, this mainly depends on the distance of the destination. Try to find a location that is reachable by a carbon-free or low-carbon transportation method. If you arrive at the destination by bike, make sure to cooperate with a bike rental store. If the destination is not accessible by bike, foot, or public transport, it will be essential to rent a private bus via a travel agency to arrange the participants' arrival.

We suggest you cooperate with university or external sports/ marathon teams in order to bridge the local community with Erasmus+ students.

Lastly, there can be a collaboration with eco-education stakeholders that can join the event by guiding the group or by giving information about the route that is planned to be taken.

Environmental considerations

- Make sure to provide the participants with all the carbon-free and low-carbon means of transport alternatives for arriving at the destination. Promote the use of public transport;
- Make sure that during the Green Marathon no one pollutes the environment by leaving trash behind or harming the local flora and fauna on the way;
- Inform the participants to bring their own reusable bottle of water or prepare a welcome bag that contains one.

Tips

- If there is a bus rental, make sure to fill all the seats on the bus (in that way each participant's carbon footprint will be minimised);
- In the case of bus/bike rental, send a participation form and ask for a participation fee prior to the rental so that the last-minute cancellations are reduced to the minimum;
- Be inclusive and do not leave anyone behind: participants of different physical stamina might join the activity, so you have to make sure to keep track of the participants so no one is left behind. Otherwise, you can split into smaller groups (with one volunteer as a Group Leader per group);
- Plan some breaks (especially for those who do not have high physical endurance) in places of environmental interest (a great viewpoint, a body of water, a rare species of plant indigenous to the area);
- When promoting the activity, try to explain with as many details as possible the character of the Marathon (distance, level of stamina needed, whether it is a competitive marathon or an opportunity for a chill outdoor activity), so that the participants who want to enrol in the activity are well aware if they can cope with the nature of it;
- You can also plan a picnic in nature, as a break or after the Marathon. Prepare beforehand the disposal of the trash, so that no trash is left by the participants or the organisers.

Example

ESN Novi Sad had planned a [similar activity](#), back in 2019. They did manage to combine physical activity and relaxation (by organising a picnic).

Garden Tour

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity, boosting urban nature.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning

- the environmental and social role of a botanical garden;
- the diversity of plants they host, and their role in saving endangered plant species from extinction.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning

- what the botanical garden of your city can offer citizens and international students in terms of education and leisure;
- to cooperate with the managing institution to tailor the visit to the group's needs and pave the way for future activities.

Time allocation

From three to six hours.

Description

As plant diversity is being lost at a high rate because of many human-caused devastating activities, botanic gardens are essential for plant species conservation, research, and public awareness and education. To learn about the world's flora, plant-human connections, biodiversity conservation, or simply spend time in a soothing environment, botanical garden tours are a perfect way to spend a half-day or a day out. To better combine leisure and education and cooperate with the botanical garden managing institution, organise a group guided tour offered by the botanical garden team. You can also ask to tailor the visit to your group's specific needs or interests. Some botanical gardens offer education workshops and activities that might be combined with a visit. Consider that, sometimes, it is possible to picnic on the grass or at the picnic tables (if any).

Target group

International students who want to understand how and why botanical gardens are so important for biodiversity and what role they play in their Erasmus hosting country.

External collaboration

Botanical gardens have guides who accompany groups during their visits. Presenting your association, the work you do with international students, and asking for a guided tour is a good way to start cooperating with a locally managed institution. Depending on your group's needs, you can ask for another activity or involve another association engaged in the research or activities of the botanical garden.

Environmental considerations

- Reach the botanical garden by bike or public transport;
- Stay on established paths and walkways. Don't walk through planted areas, climb on trees and rocks. Don't wade in ponds or fountains;
- Never remove plants, seeds, flowers, fruit, stones, or anything else. Leave the botanical garden as you found it;
- If you can do a picnic, do not leave any rubbish behind and collect the one you found even if it is not yours.

Tips

- To avoid dropouts, ask participants to partially pay in advance to secure their attendance if there is an entrance fee. You might benefit from a group discount only if the minimum number is reached;
- Check the accessibility and facilities for people with disabilities and inform the guide of their needs;
- When you promote this activity, focus on the leisure side and stress the learning outcomes mentioned above.

Example

ESN Aure Camerino organised a [tour of the Botanical Garden of their city](#) to let international students discover the cultural importance of this garden to the city.

Reserve Guided Tour

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity, promoting slow and sustainable travel.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning

- about the biodiversity of the city and country where they are spending their exchange time;
- the importance of biodiversity conservation and its benefits;
- to cooperate with local associations and institutions.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning how to

- organise a visit to a natural reserve;
- manage and guide participants outside of urban areas;
- establish partnerships with local associations and/or institutions;
- convey key messages about sustainable tourism and nature conservation.

Time allocation

From four hours to one day.

Description

The first step to nature conservation is to gain knowledge about such nature. Moreover, biodiversity is one of the main heritages of an area. Hence, by visiting a local natural reserve, the participants will be able to experience one of the most important aspects of the culture of the area they are spending their exchange period in, and learn about the local nature and how to actually conserve it. If it is possible, you could propose volunteering activities at the reserve: in this way, the participants could both learn and experience biodiversity.

Target group

Any international student eager to know more about the local fauna and flora (with attention to accessibility needs).

External collaboration

You need to collaborate with the institution or association in charge of the area you are planning to visit. Even if it is possible to do the tour on your own, we recommend the presence of a local guide that can explain to the participants the species and ecosystems present and the main threats they are facing.

Environmental considerations

- Try to reach the natural reserve by using sustainable means of transport: foot, bike or public transport;
- Pick up the rubbish if you see it, even if it is not yours;
- If you plan to have lunch within the reserve, try to avoid plastic and single-use materials and tell the participants to bring their own reusable bottles and cutlery (if needed);
- Recycle your rubbish;
- Do not pick up plants or leave the trail, and listen carefully to what the guide tells you.

Tips

- To avoid dropouts, set a deposit to secure participants' registration and participation: you will give it back as soon as they show up to the event;
- To better promote the event, you can do a social campaign on biodiversity and consider this event as the last on-field part of the activity;
- If the reserve is managed by a local association, ask them to present themselves and how the participants could get involved; moreover, try to implement the tour with some volunteering activities;
- When you promote this activity, focus on the leisure side and stress the learning outcomes mentioned above;
- After the activity, ask the participants for feedback on the messages conveyed by the event and make them reflect on such issues.

Examples

Have a look at these activities organised by ESN Politecnico Milano:

- [WWF Wildlife Oasis Trip 2020](#)
- [WWF Wildlife Oasis Trip 2021](#)

They combined the exploration of a naturalistic area with some volunteering activities to maintain it, and established a collaboration with WWF in the meanwhile.

City Wild Plants Tour

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity, boosting urban nature.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning how to recognise the wild corners of a city, their potential and why it is important to encourage natural processes for biodiversity conservation. You might propose a similar activity in your city.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning how to recognise the wild corners of your city, their potential and why it is important to encourage natural processes for biodiversity conservation thanks to the help and guidance of an association active in the management and protection of urban nature. You might become the next guide!

Time allocation

Two to three hours.

Description

More than half of the people on Earth live in cities, and it is not always necessary to be immersed in a forest to observe nature. Pockets of biodiversity can be found in city parks, residential areas, and abandoned zones in and around the city. Even a sidewalk or a private garden wall, at closer sight, reveals the great potential and strength of nature. A walking tour of this kind allows you to look at your city with different eyes, know the species that blend themselves into the human-made environment, and understand which ones are suitable for your personal use! Partner up with a local association active in the management and protection of urban nature to guide your group in this adventure. You can also combine this tour with a visit to an urban vegetable garden to find out the social and environmental value of this type of horticulture.

Target group

International students who want to learn how biodiversity can be protected and enhanced in the urban areas of their Erasmus host city.

External collaboration

Contact an association active in the management and protection of urban nature. Sometimes local authorities are in charge of this aspect or have a policy to protect the biodiversity in the city. Explain the goal of your activity and the multiplier effect it might have once international students go back home.

If you combine this tour with a visit to an urban vegetable garden, contact the managing association/institution and check with them on how and if international students can volunteer.

Environmental considerations

- Help to preserve the green spots you visit by collecting the rubbish you find on the way. Similarly, observe and clean the green spots close to your accommodation;
- If you want to forage some herbs or berries, do not try to eat them if you are not 100% sure of what they are;
- Dry herbs correctly. Oven drying is a good way to stay on the safe side.

Tips

- Check the route and inform the association or authority you are in contact with about accessibility needs;
- When you promote this activity, focus on the leisure side and stress the learning outcomes mentioned above.

Scuba Diving

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity.

Learning outcome for the participants

- Trying out a new outdoor activity before officially adopting it as a hobby;
- Learning about the necessity of environmental protection for aquatic ecosystems;
- Raising awareness for the local aquatic fauna and flora.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning how to

- organise a scuba diving event for Erasmus+ students;
- manage a group of students while doing an outdoor activity;
- organise green events with a low carbon emission footprint.

Time allocation

Half to full day.

Description

A scuba diving event gives the Erasmus+ students the opportunity to learn a new sports skill and be aware of the importance of the sustainability of aquatic environments. This activity is preferable to be organised by a student association that can easily reach the sea by foot, bike, or low-carbon means of transport such as buses or trains.

Before diving in the ocean/sea, learn how to use the equipment correctly and safely via demonstration from a specialist. A presentation by an NGO will give participants the chance to understand the local aquatic fauna and flora and their importance to the local ecosystem. For the participants that feel unsafe trying scuba diving, give them the chance to try another activity such as snorkelling, again with the supervision of an expert.

Once you are underwater you will be able to admire the beauties of the ocean (or in a bad scenario the pollution of the aquatic environment). The scuba diving activity can also be organised as an underwater clean-up activity so that you collect all the underwater rubbish and dispose of it correctly. In this case, this activity can be addressed also as a waste and recycling theme and not only as a biodiversity-themed one. Enjoy a walk or a picnic at the beach when the diving is over.

Target group

International students who wish to try out scuba diving (or snorkelling) as a sports activity and are already familiar with swimming.

External collaboration

This activity can only be organised if you cooperate with a scuba diving/ underwater sports facility. Once you communicate with one and know where the facility is located, find the way of transportation to the place of interest. There might be a need to collaborate with a travel agency in order to rent a bus (or a minibus if the number of participants is small), to book train tickets etc. You can also turn to bike rental if the destination is reachable by bike.

Cooperate with eco-educational NGOs to provide participants (and the organisers) with interesting information about the underwater ecosystem they are about to dive in and explain the need to preserve it. In case of a scuba diving clean-up of the sea bottom, cooperate with other environmental groups to help you up.

Environmental considerations

- Consider arriving at the facility by foot or bike (zero carbon emission) or by public transportation/train. As a last resort, consider a bus, but try to use all of its capacity so that the carbon footprint of each person is the minimum possible.
- Let the participants know that they cannot litter the sea or the beach and should be respectful of the environment.
- Prepare (as a side activity) a beach or a sea bottom clean-up.
- In case of welcome bag preparation try to minimise the non-reusable materials/equipment and in case of a picnic as a side activity, bring food and drinks that are not in plastic containers.

Tips

Set a participation fee and a deadline for payment at least one day prior to the event. That way, participants will not cancel at the last minute. On the participation form, inform the participants that they cannot participate in the activity if they don't watch the demonstration from the scuba diving facility staff. It is important for the safety of the group.

Example

There have been multiple scuba diving activities by [ESN Palermo](#), [ESN Canakkale](#) and [ESN Malta](#) (and a second one from [ESN Malta](#)). All of those sections managed to raise awareness of the local aquatic ecosystems among the Erasmus+ students and gave them the opportunity to try a different sport.

Mushroom Picking

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity, promoting slow and sustainable travel.

Learning outcome for the participants

- Learning about the local mushroom species;
- Meeting up with local experts and/or associations;
- Reflecting upon the environmental impact of the food we eat;
- Learning which mushrooms to pick up and how to do it without affecting the environment.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning how to

- organise an original trip in the local area;
- establish partnerships with local associations and environmental guides.

Time allocation

Four to six hours.

Description

Mushrooms are a key element of several countries' food culture but little is known about them: What is their biology? Which species are edible, which are not, and how do I recognise them? What is their role in the ecosystem?

To answer all these questions, you could organise a mushroom-picking trip in collaboration with a local expert. This collaboration is mandatory: indeed, it is very easy to make mistakes on which fungal species are edible and which are not and that can be very dangerous. Afterwards, the foraged mushrooms could be used in a cooking lesson in order to convey the message of the

importance of slow food. This way, the international students could learn about a core element of the biodiversity of the area and about some of the typical food recipes of the country they are spending their exchange period in.

Target group

Any international student curious about the local mushroom diversity and how to cook edible ones.

External collaboration

For this kind of activity, you need to set up a partnership with local experts or associations/NGOs. It is very important for multiple reasons: they know which species are edible and which are not (you need to be extra careful about that), they know what amount you can collect without affecting the environment, and they can explain to the participants about the area and the local mushroom biodiversity.

Environmental considerations

- Try to reach where the activity will be carried on by using sustainable means of transport: on foot, bike or public transport;
- Do not talk loud or scream: it might disturb the local fauna;
- Do not leave the trail and pick up rubbish you find, even if it is not yours.

Tips

- To better promote the event, you can do a social campaign on the impact of food, maybe in an interactive way;
- After the activity, ask the participants for feedback on the messages conveyed by the event and make them reflect on such issues.

Example

Have a look at this [mushroom picking organised by ESN Trento](#): they also made a sustainable picnic within the forest they made the activity in.

An alternative could also be local herbs or berry picking, either also for cooking or also for medical purposes. ESN Iasi for example organised an online edition of [Edible Wild Plants](#).

Workshops

Compost and Worm Compost

Objectives

Fostering a circular economy, reducing waste and promoting recycling.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning the value of composting and bonding with Erasmus and local students through a green activity.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning how to

- organise a workshop concerning composting and worm composting;
- communicate with the university administration about the establishment of composting facilities within the campus area;
- promote a green activity in a way that sounds appealing for the Erasmus+ students.

Time allocation

From two to six hours.

Description

Composting organic materials can reduce the total waste of a household or a person, thus making it a habit worth adopting. A facilitator (whether an experienced member of your student association or an external partner) will explain the theory behind composting and the necessity of acquiring it as a habit. You will sort out the rubbish (brought from home or given by the facilitator) and put

in the compost pile the ones compatible with the composting process. Participants interested in continuing composting at home will be given the composting worms at the end of the workshop.

Target group

Anyone interested in learning about composting or in general anyone who is or wants to become environmentally aware while on an Erasmus+ mobility programme.

External collaboration

Cooperate with eco-educational associations that can lead a workshop on the topic, with professors from environmental and/or agricultural sciences who can provide the theoretical framework, and with the Entomology laboratory of your University for the composting worms provision.

The student association members can communicate with the university administration, in order to establish a composting facility on the campus, not only for the workshop but overall for the reduction of waste at the university as a whole.

If the workshop cannot be organised on the university campus, it can be held at a farm or a composting facility.

Environmental considerations

- Choose a location that is easily reachable by foot, bike, public transport or train;
- After the separation of the waste as compostable and non-compostable, make sure to properly dispose of/recycle the non-compostable materials;
- Ask the participants to bring their own containers (or provide them with one made of eco-friendly material) in case they want to take the worm compost back home.

Tips

- Ask the participants to fill out a form of participation to be aware of the exact number of participants;
- Set a minor fee in order to minimise the last-minute cancellation;
- The group interested in this workshop should gather in the place where it will take place with casual fit clothes because they might get dirty.

Example

The AVRDC has made a [guide](#) on how to prepare a composting workshop that explains the theory behind composting and directs you on how to facilitate such workshops.

Creating Seed Bombs

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity, boosting urban nature.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning how to create seed bombs and what the secrets are to make them flourish.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning how to

- organise a workshop concerning composting lead a fun activity;
- make university areas greener and cooperate with the agro-science department to find the perfect soil for your activity.

Time allocation

Two hours.

Description

Creating seed bombs is a funny activity used to create vegetation in small areas, such as gardens and allotments, which look desolate. Participants will learn how to pack seed bombs with nutrients for a head-start and which are the most suitable soils for tossing them. For a successful activity, organisers should contact a professor or a researcher from the agro-sciences department of your university to find the perfect spot in your university campus or garden to host the seed bombs, as they cannot flourish everywhere.

Target group

International students who are interested in learning about this activity or want to make their Erasmus+ city greener.

External collaboration

Making seed bombs is not difficult, but there are some instructions that it is important to follow for a successful activity. That is why it is important to involve a professor or a researcher of the agro-science department of your university (unless a member of your organisation is experienced in this) to find a spot with suitable soil properties to toss them. Ask the same department or the university administration for a room where you can create your bombs. Organisers can also involve local associations active in city-plant greenery. They might know other spots where you can reproduce the activity or show you a seed-bombed area where results are already visible.

Environmental considerations

- Buy the seeds in an organic shop or nursery and ask for suggestions from the
- agro-science department of your university;
- You might need bowls and/or glasses for this activity. As they can be easily
- found in any home, ask participants to bring them to avoid single-use items.

Tips

- Have a look at this article by the Wildlife Trusts and at these 10 rules by Seed Bomb City to find out the secrets for a perfect seed bomb;
- Inform the participants that it is better to wear comfortable and delicate clothes. Clay is among the ingredients;
- Do not think of tossing seed bombs in meadowland or compacted soil. Do your research and consult the experts as suggested above.

Recognising Biodiversity by its Traces

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning how to

- recognise urban and non-urban biodiversity;
- take a picture of it without generating an environmental impact.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning how to organise a workshop on biodiversity, collaborate with other associations and experts and how to convey the message of nature conservation.

Time allocation

From three to four hours to a whole day.

Description

There is more biodiversity around us than you could ever imagine. This activity will allow the participants to recognise the presence of non-human species by its traces and to look for it without any negative impact. In particular, this activity is composed of two parts:

- The first session with one or more naturalistic experts that will allow the participants to notice the subtle traces that biodiversity leaves and how to recognise which species leave which traces;
- A second session where the participants will learn how to find the species that live around us and how to recognise which behaviour stresses them.

Target group

Anyone interested in learning about the biodiversity of their Erasmus+ destination.

External collaboration

You need to collaborate with environmental scientists in order to have appropriate sessions.

Environmental considerations

- Try to reach the location where you will have the sessions by using sustainable means of transport: foot, bike, or public transport;
- Pick up the trash if you see it, even if it is not yours;
- If you plan to have lunch within the place, try to avoid plastic and single-use materials and tell the participants to bring their own both; moreover, recycle your trash;
- Convey the key message of nature conservation from the first moment: recognising biodiversity is only the first step to protect it.

Tips

- To avoid uncontrolled backouts, set a participation fee or a deposit to secure participants' registration and participation;
- To better promote the event, you can do a social campaign on biodiversity and consider this event as the last on-field part of the activity;
- When you promote this activity, focus on the possibility to see lots of species and stress the learning outcomes mentioned above;
- After the activity, ask the participants for feedback on the messages conveyed by the event and make them reflect on such issues;
- Try to make the activity more entertaining, by asking questions and interacting directly with the participants during the sessions.

Campaigns

Cycle and Pedestrian Green Paths

Objectives

Promoting slow and sustainable travel, boosting urban nature.

Learning outcome for the participants

- Learning what the benefits of the cycle and pedestrian green routes are;
- Contributing to a cause that you can propose to your city once back;
- Striving for a greener city for the benefit of the next Erasmus students.

Learning outcome for the organisers

- Enhancing the network with other local associations and develop a partnership for a common long-term cause;
- Learning how to engage international students in a city-focused campaign that can be a model for their city once they are back, or they can contribute to if they have experience on this matter.

Time allocation

Since a campaign can last months, we do not propose a precise timescale for this. To organise an event within a campaign such as a march, the time might depend on the length of the march and collateral activities (a picnic or a concert for example).

Description

Cycle and pedestrian green routes are an essential part of the green networks in a city. They provide recreational public health and well-being opportunities as well as connect cyclists and pedestrians to nature. The result is a general increase in quality of life, which also positively affects

an Erasmus experience. Unfortunately, not all cities have developed an extensive network like this, and raising awareness about their importance is something that a student association can do. To let international students understand the city's current urban structure and its possible green development, it is essential that the organisers partner up with other local associations that strive to develop bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure. A march by bike and foot on a route appropriate for such a development is a good way to (re)launch a campaign about the cycle and pedestrian green routes. Explore other ideas with your local partners. Connected to this green network city plan, you can advocate for bike-sharing programmes at convenient locations on campus, discounted access to municipal or private bike-sharing schemes and organise bike self-repair workshops or free bike repair events.

Target group

International students who want to contribute to the slow travel and green mobility of their hosting cities.

External collaboration

Nowadays, everyone recognises the importance of cycle and pedestrian green routes, but sometimes the link between a green city and internationalisation is not that immediate. Green credentials might be considered by environmentally conscious students when choosing their Erasmus destination. Raise this argument to join a campaign with other local associations that strive to develop bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure or start a new campaign with local actors to boost the attractiveness of your city (and university) by making it greener. When organising the march, either as the main organiser or as a partner of another association, it is mandatory to cooperate with the municipality and get the right permissions.

Green Up Our Lives

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning about how to practise nature conservation.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning how to

- convey the message that nature conservation starts from all of us;
- collaborate with other associations, experts and institutions.

Time allocation

A series of brief activities spread across the semester.

Description

Biodiversity is disappearing from our streets, replaced by ever-growing urbanisation. That is why it is fundamental to campaign about the importance of nature in our lives and show participants how to implement biodiversity in their homes. More in detail, the organisers could develop a “biodiversity at home” campaign enriched by several concrete actions such as small tree planting in private or public gardens (with prior authority’s approval), the establishment of a vegetable garden at the university campus, the growth of seeds from aromatic plants, the design of bird, bee and bat boxes. In this way, the international students could learn how to conserve biodiversity in their homes and streets and give this information back to their local communities when they go back home.

Target group

International students interested in preserving and boosting biodiversity during their exchange.

External collaboration

Before each of the events, you could invite guests and experts from different local associations to help you explain the advantages provided by biodiversity to humans and to better understand which actions are required to green up our lives. This could be a nice training, in order for everyone to carry on with the indoor experiments more properly and with more understanding.

Environmental considerations

- Concerning trees and seeds, always ask experts which species are more beneficial to the local environment and not detrimental to native species;
- If your activity is focused on vegetable gardens and aromatic plants, stress the importance of sustainable choices concerning food.

Tips

- To better promote the event, you can do a social campaign on the importance of nature conservation and stress that this project will be composed of different activities;
- When you promote this activity, focus on the possibility to see more species within private and public gardens, universities, public spaces, etc. if they manage to carry out the actions you suggested;
- The project could be finalised by an event in the university with the involvement of institutions: this could let you establish a more fruitful partnership with such institutions and make the participants realise how impactful their activities have been.

Volunteering on Exchange

Saving Animals

Objectives

Protecting nature, promoting biodiversity and encouraging wildlife protection.

Learning outcome for the participants

- Learning how to protect endangered species;
- Raising awareness about wildlife protection and contribute to the environmental causes of your Erasmus+ destination.

Learning outcome for the organisers

- Learning how to organise a saving animals activity (or a trip, in case it is more than one day);
- Raising awareness about the local fauna.

Time allocation

Half a day to three days.

Description

This activity can be organised as a one- or multiple-day trip in cooperation with an animal rescue and wildlife protection association. Once you visit the facility and learn all the useful information about the local fauna and the dangers it is facing due to human activities, help the association staff practically (provide them with veterinary aid, food and water or release them back into the wild). Additionally, you may follow the trails of animals and observe their behaviour (from a safe distance to ensure that you do not scare the animals and avoid accidents).

Target group

International students who are interested in raising awareness about the fauna of their Erasmus+ mobility destination and the struggles they face because of human activity.

External collaboration

You will have to communicate with a facility that rescues animals or with a wildlife protection association that can provide you with theoretical and practical information on the topic. Also, cooperation with a travel agency to organise transportation there is mandatory, especially if the facility is unreachable by foot or public transport. In case of a multiple-day trip, you will also have to book accommodation to host the group. Preferably choose a hostel or a Bed & Breakfast with a green philosophy.

Environmental considerations

- Organise transportation with low-carbon or carbon-free ways of transport. In the case of renting a bus, make sure that it is used at its full potential (in that way each person's carbon footprint is minimised);
- In case of a multiple-day trip, you can prepare welcome bags with reusable materials in order to reduce each participant's waste;
- Let the participants know that they have to respect the local ecosystem and not litter the environment or scare the animals by making too much noise.

Tips

- Arrange a stay at a camp to live a green trip experience;
- Set a participation fee with a deadline prior to the day of departure to minimise last-minute cancellations.

Examples

Some examples of associations you can cooperate with for this kind of activity are

- *In Greece:* [Saving Turtles \(Caretta caretta\)](#), [Saving Seals \(Monachus monachus\)](#), [General Wildlife](#);
- *In Italy:* [Legambiente](#), [LIPU](#), [ANPANA](#);
- *In Sweden:* [Djurskyddet Sverige](#).

Cigarette Butts Clean-up

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity, reducing waste and promoting recycling.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning how impactful cigarette butts' litter is on the environment and living beings' wellness.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning how to

- raise awareness on cigarette butts litter and how it wrecks the environment and compromises humans' and animals' health;
- to involve an environmental association in your activity to understand the impact of this type of pollution.

Time allocation

Two hours or more depending on the place you organise it and the distance to reach it.

Description

According to the [Truth Initiative](#), cigarettes are the most littered item with about 4.5 trillion butts of cigarettes tossed each year. They are made of plastic fibres which emit toxic chemicals into the environment and contaminate water. Cigarette butts clean-up is an easy activity to organise and suitable to show that, despite their tiny size, they pollute considerably. For example, the Ocean Conservancy has noticed that cigarette butts account for one in every five items found in their annual Coastal Clean-ups. Therefore, organise this activity in heavily cigarette-polluted areas such as beaches, nightlife districts, canals, lakes, riverfronts, city parks or bus stops. You can calculate the impact of the butts clean-up through [Omni Calculator](#). Organise this activity with the cooperation of a local association that is active in the preservation of coasts as well as canal

and river sides. They could share information and campaigns specifically focusing on this kind of pollution.

Target group

Anyone who wants to contribute to a cleaner Erasmus+ hosting city.

External collaboration

Map the associations that are active in the no-waste and environmental field and pick the most suitable one for your activity. For example, if you live in a city with a river or a canal, there might be associations committed to preserving the water ecosystems in urban areas. If such associations do not exist, involve any local environmental association to promote the cause and organise the activity together.

Environmental considerations

- This is an activity you can organise in a park as well as in a non-urban area. In this case, mind the means of transport. It is preferable to use a carbon-free (walking, bikes) or a low carbon (train, bus) transportation;
- Collect the cigarette butts in glass jars. You can wash and reuse them for your next activity once you dispose of the litter in the undifferentiated waste bag. For sanitary reasons, the participants will need gloves. Make sure that they are made of biodegradable, or even better, compostable materials.

Tips

- Check the weather for the day to avoid rain or heat waves. The activity will not be pleasant under these circumstances. If the weather allows, combine this activity with a picnic or other outdoor activities;
- If you need to use a bus to reach your destination, set a participation fee to minimise last-minute cancellations.

Examples

- Cigarette butts cleaning can also be competitive and ESN Torino knows something about it. [Check out their activity.](#)

Canal/River/Lake Clean-up

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity, reducing waste and promoting recycling.

Learning outcome for the participants

Understanding the level of waste issues in natural bodies of water.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning how to

- organise an outdoor activity of a body of water clean-up;
- manage a group of people in a green activity;
- promote an environment-oriented event.

Time allocation

Half to a full day.

Description

Everyone has been on a trip to nature, all excited to visit a water body and then got disappointed by the excessive waste. Clean-up groups restore a place's beauty. You can organise the transportation to the destination in need of cleaning and, as a group, collect and properly sort out the rubbish into compostable, recyclable and other waste. At the end of the day, having gathered the total amount of litter, you can dispose of them accordingly. Once the environment of the lake/canal/river is free of rubbish, you may organise a picnic or some group game contest before you head back home.

Target group

Anyone who is interested in outdoor activities with a positive impact on the environment of their Erasmus+ destination.

External collaboration

You can contact an eco-educational association that can provide useful knowledge for the local fauna and flora and address the necessity of the clean-up activity for the ecosystem. Additionally, you may communicate with other environmental and volunteering groups of the university for assistance in the project.

Finally, you might have to cooperate with a bike rental store or a travel agency to address the transportation to the destination.

Environmental considerations

- Consider the way of transportation to the destination. It is preferred to use a carbon-free means of transportation (walking, bikes) or a low carbon emitting way (train, bus);
- Make sure that the participants are disposing of the waste the correct way (for example separating the plastics from organics);
- For sanitary reasons, the participants will need gloves. Make sure that they are made of biodegradable or compostable materials.

Tips

- Check the weather for the day. You don't want the activity to take place either during a storm or a heatwave. Also, if the weather is nice you can organise a picnic or other outdoor activities;
- Set a participation fee in case of a bus rental for minimising last-minute cancellations.

Examples

Have a look at [this activity](#) organised by ESN Genova, they used kayaks to clean up a canal in their city.

Planting Trees

Objectives

Protecting nature and promoting biodiversity, boosting urban nature.

Learning outcome for the participants

- Learning about the ecosystem advantages of trees and green space in urban areas;
- Meeting up with local experts and/or associations, and reaffirm the importance of active citizenship.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning a practice of nature conservation, establish partnerships with local associations and/or institutions.

Time allocation

From a couple of hours to one-day.

Description

Shade, absorption of CO₂ and other gases, increased biodiversity and improved air quality: these are only a few of the benefits that our trees provide us. Tree planting, therefore, is an activity that allows international students to have a significant impact on the city that is hosting them. The activity could be coupled with a clean-up of the area and should be open to the whole community: in the learning-by-doing approach, international students should be the ones to manage the activity and could experience directly how their actions can affect their community.

Target group

Anyone who wants to make Erasmus+ cities greener.

External collaboration

Collaborating with a local environmental association is strongly recommended: they know better how to carry out this kind of activity.

For instance, they can tell you what species of plants are better for the environment and which is the best season to plant them. Be careful to avoid planting alien and invasive species: they could be very detrimental to the environment!

Before the tree planting, you can organise a meeting with the NGO in order to train your international students about the benefits of trees and tree planting. This activity could also help you create or strengthen collaborations with institutions: for example the city hall and the university.

Environmental considerations

- Try to reach where the activity will be carried out by using sustainable means of transport: walking, bike or public transport;
- If you plan to eat during your activity, ask participants to bring their own reusable bottles, cutlery and lunch boxes and avoid plastic and single-use materials;
- Always ask experts on how to carry out your tree planting: they can help you in choosing the proper time, place and trees to plant.

Tips

- To better promote the event, you can do a social campaign on biodiversity and consider this event as the last on-site part of the activity;
- If your tree planting will be located in a reserve, try to organise a guided visit to it;
- Promote the event to the whole local community and try to involve several associations and institutions;
- After the activity, ask the participants for feedback on the messages conveyed by the event and make them reflect on such issues;
- You could combine tree planting with different activities: clean-ups, nature walks, environmentally-based games, presentations of various associations, flash mobs...

Examples

Have a look at these activities:

- [Tree Planting - ESN Politecnico Milano](#);
- [Urban Regeneration with Legambiente Catania - ESN Catania](#);
- [Planting Trees - ESN Ioannina](#);
- [Tree Plantation - ESN Alcalá](#).

AWARENESS AND ACTIVISM

This section proposes activities that can facilitate learning about the topics of the climate crisis or any other justice issue that you might want to get vocal about.

LESS MEAT

=
LESS HEAT!

NOW

STUDENTS FOR CLIMATE
PLANET

STUDENTS FOR CLIMATE
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#FROKKAUST
STUDENTS FOR CLIMATE
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STUDENTS FOR CLIMATE
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for a
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PLANET

WHERE IS
JUSTICE

Events

Human/Living Library

Objective

Fighting climate crisis.

Learning outcome for the participants

Gaining first-hand insights from the experience and perspective of environmental activists and experts.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Working with environmental activists and experts during the preparation of the event and get to know their work beforehand.

Time allocation

Two hours.

Description

The goal of human libraries is to create a space where people can meet and hear stories of those they might not normally meet. Instead of books, people learn about certain topics through the experiences and stories of other humans. It can give international students the chance to learn from local experts about local environmental challenges. At the same time, international students can act as “human books” and share stories from their own countries with local students or groups of people.

For the exact process, each participant, or a group of participants, has the opportunity to “borrow”, as we do with books, one expert at a time to ask them questions, to debate or just to discuss the opportunities that society, enterprises and academic institutions could leverage to fight against

the environmental and climate crises.

It is important to invite experts who have worked actively on environmental topics, so their stories can inspire participants and visitors to engage in environmental issues.

Target group

International students interested in learning about the environmental challenges of the hosting country and sharing the ones from their homeland.

External collaboration

- NGOs, independent organisations and global campaigning networks which can send experts to participate in the event;
- Universities and environmental sciences faculties;
- Youth centres as the venues for the event.

Environmental considerations

Make sure to not print unnecessarily.

Tips

With the agreement of the participants, and respecting the GDPR law, organisers should try to keep the contact details of participants and visitors in case they want to know more about the experts and their organisations such as Greenpeace, Food and Water Watch, WWF or even Conservation International (CI).

Examples

Have a look at some similar events:

- [Visit to the Experimental Field of Iasi University of Life Sciences;](#)
- [EU Green Week of Selcuk University;](#)
- [Climate Change and Food Security: Future scenarios.](#)

COP Simulation of Youth

Objective

Fighting climate crisis.

Learning outcome for the participants

Gaining an insight into international climate negotiation processes and positions of different countries.

Time allocation

One to two hours preparation, two hours event.

Description

Each year in autumn the Conference of Parties (COP) on climate change is organised by the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). It is a large event where key decision makers meet to discuss progress and action on the climate crisis - e.g. in 2015 the [Paris Agreement](#) was adopted. Civil society has limited access to the event which is problematic as groups represented by NGOs, including young people, should have a say in the transformation of society and plans made to tackle the crisis. Therefore, the idea of this event is to (1) introduce young people to what COP actually is and how it works and (2) create a consultation of young people on what they believe should be discussed at COP.

Organisers are invited to group people into country teams and provide them with some information on the state of climate policy, the exposure to impacts of climate change etc. from that country. Ideally, people would represent their own countries, drawing on first-hand experience or knowledge. Then, the consultation process starts where different questions might be asked, for

example about the future of the food system, and different people can share their thoughts and discuss.

Target group

International students who are interested in international climate politics and want to take advantage of their Erasmus experience to be more engaged.

External collaboration

Do you want to be more engaged in international climate politics, but you do not know where to start from, or you do not feel knowledgeable enough? Partner with associations such as [Generation Climate Europe](#), [YOUNGO](#), European Youth Forum, the national COP delegation or local climate groups.

Environmental considerations

Make sure that organisers/trainers stay scientific and use legitimate sources of information to avoid the spread of false information.

Tips

Organisers should pay specific attention to the structure of the consultation and how it is moderated.

Prepare resources (e.g. with help of Generation Climate Europe) on where to find the latest climate science for different countries and what are the conditions and solutions for example proposed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the largest body of researchers reviewing scientific evidence on climate change.

Examples

- [COP26 simulation](#)

Documentary Screening

Objective

Can be any of the objectives of this guide and even beyond.

Learning outcome for the participants

- Increasing awareness of environmental issues and politicising them;
- Learning the connection of environmental issues with social, economic and technical issues and how they all interrelate.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning how to organise an event and facilitate some small discussions.

Time allocation

To two to three hours depending on the documentary.

Description

The idea of this event is to choose a certain environmental documentary and screen the film. This can be in line with current topics (e.g. connection between war and the climate crisis) or times of the year (e.g. Earth Day in April). The topic can also be chosen based on the local context and economy (e.g. fishing industry for cities on the coast).

The session itself can start with a little icebreaker to get people to reflect on what they know about the issues. In the end, a little reflection round can be held where people share in small groups or in plenary what they learned. Sometimes an expert panel could be invited to discuss the film, potentially in a fishbowl format where participants also have the chance to engage through an open chair.

Target group

International students with an interest in different political topics.

External collaboration

Depending on the issue that is covered local actors working on these problems or solutions for them can be invited (for example to discuss with the audience after the film). Sometimes it might be possible to invite a film director if it is a smaller film. Local cinemas or film festivals might also collaborate.

Environmental considerations

Make sure to only screen movies that you know are authentic and well-researched with recent sources.

Tips

Try to have an informal icebreaker before starting, so participants can share the reason why they are interested in the subject. Also, it is very important to have a reflection round at the end, maybe a short panel session with a seat reserved for an audience member. Depending on the topic of the documentary, reflection is also needed on what can be done at a local level to act on the issue addressed.

Workshops

How to Design a Campaign?

Objective

Can be any of the objectives of this guide and even beyond.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning and implementing the different steps of the process of organising a campaign about a specific topic such as climate crisis, climate justice, waste pollution or animal welfare. Those steps will depend on the type of campaign (advocacy or behaviour change) to be developed.

Time allocation

One and a half hours to a day, depending on whether participants design an actual campaign in the workshop.

Description

Learning to design a campaign to defend a cause needs a lot of preparation - a campaign has to set clear goals about what it should achieve and how it will be achieved. It is important to cover the most important topics about how to design a campaign such as:

- setting the goal(s) and target audience;
- developing tactics and strategies for outreach and narrative;
- defining the leadership of the campaign;
- assembling the team;

Learning outcome for the organisers

Acquiring more experience holding workshops on one of the topics.

- assigning tasks;
- conducting research for planning (issue research, environment research, stakeholder research, solution research, target research and/or audience research);
- following up on the research and feedback.

Trainers will decide on the best methodologies to help participants learn what is required to design a campaign and as an evaluation method participants will design a campaign about a meaningful environmental topic.

Target group

- People who want to advocate for an idea, a project or a concept by creating, planning and conducting a campaign at the local, national or international level;
- Trainers who are willing to gain more experience in holding workshops on such topics.

External collaboration

- Trainers with knowledge and experience in campaigning about environmental crises and environmental protection;
- Experts from NGOs for mentoring trainers in terms of the content and methodologies used during the training;
- Youth centres.

Environmental considerations

- Use online boards and post-its like Mural, Miro or NoteBookCast instead of using paper;
- When the participants are designing the campaign, use acrylic whiteboards instead of paper or cartons.

Tips

- In order to make the training more attractive, the organisers and trainers should consolidate partnerships with environmental NGOs to use these workshops' outputs in these organisations' campaigns;
- Launch the open call for participants for other student associations to open the door for future collaborations with them.

Examples

ESN local sections have not prepared a workshop about "How to design a campaign" per se, but some interesting ideas that would be interesting to implement as a concrete result from a campaign are:

- [Think Reusable with ESN EYE](#);
- [Social\(ize\): Let's design ECO bags together](#);
- [Collage Workshop](#).

How to Organise a Protest/Event Yourself about a Topic?

Objective

Can be any of the objectives of this guide and even beyond.

Learning outcome for the participants

Gaining skills and knowledge on event organisation and the related logistical challenges (timing, legal questions).

Learning outcome for the organisers

The facilitators will extend their skills in hosting an event, training and passing on their expertise.

Time allocation

One to two hours or it can be part of a series.

Description

Much of the Green Erasmus activities suggested here are centred around events that need to be organised. While people often just learn by doing, this activity would have the purpose of empowering young people to organise a political event such as a protest or action to raise awareness of certain political topics. Independently of the exact topic, this activity thus targets skills development. This is especially useful for international students who have a chance to engage with local networks and environmental themes through organising events or campaigns.

Target group

Young local politically engaged/interested people who want to organise an event/action/protest.

External collaboration

Collaborations could happen with local social movements that focus on local issues or local branches of more national or international social movements as those can provide expert

knowledge. Another possible cooperation could be with communities or groups that are affected by a certain problem and share their perspective on what matters for designing an action or protest well.

Environmental considerations

Event organisation is to bring people together, so organisers should make sure that the location can be reached by public or sustainable means of transport and ensure the correct waste disposal.

Tips

- Use knowledge from local groups;
- Implement enough breaks and ice-breakers.

Crash Course in Climate Science

Objective

Fighting the climate crisis.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning the basics about the earth's systems and how key economic activities drive environmental degradation and the increasing instability of these systems.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Trainers will deepen their ability to convey knowledge by holding workshops about sustainability and the environmental crisis.

Time allocation

Workshop: One and a half to three hours, could be over several days or in a workshop series.

Description

Many people have accepted that the climate crisis is occurring, and young people worry about the impact it will have on their future. To be equipped for debates on the topic and really comprehend the severity of the situation, this activity aims to deliver a crash course in climate science. It can cover the main drivers of climate change, including the role of humans in general, and who is particularly responsible (e.g. the richest 10 percent of people produce half of the planet's individual-consumption-based fossil fuel emissions ([Oxfam: 2015](#))). It should also mention the [Milankovitch cycles](#) and other scientific arguments that have led climate scientists to conclude that climate change has anthropogenic causes.

The workshop would be aimed at explaining for example the interconnectedness of global warming, deforestation, war, energy production, and food systems. It could be part of a series of workshops focusing on different elements of the climate crisis, e.g. gender and climate, war and climate, democracy and climate, etc.

Part of the workshop (series) could be to brainstorm how to better communicate climate science.

Target group

- People who want to learn more about the current global situation in terms of climate change;
- Trainers who are willing to gain more experience in holding workshops on such topics.

External collaboration

- Experienced trainers with knowledge of environmental crisis and environmental protection/ environmental science students;
- Experts from NGOs for mentoring trainers in terms of the content and methodologies used during the training.

Environmental considerations

- Use online boards and post-its like Mural, Miro or NoteBookCast instead of using paper;
- If the participants are designing the campaign, it would be preferable to use acrylic whiteboards instead of paper or carton or make sure that the materials will be recycled.

Tips

- Make sure to review which trainers are delivering the workshops. Check their materials, including whether they use credible references. Only invite trainers who have actually studied the subject;
- In order to make the training more attractive, the organisers and trainers should consolidate partnerships with environmental NGOs to use the outputs from these workshops in these institutions' campaigns.

Environmental Education at Higher Education Institutions

Objectives

Fighting the climate crisis, fostering responsible consumption.

Learning outcome for the participants

Understanding the impact of their HEI on climate change and the different leverage points of change for an institution to change.

Learning outcome for the organisers

Learning to lead the discussion and stimulate the debate about the impact of university on climate and how they can contribute to sustainability.

Time allocation

One to three hours.

Description

Around the world, there is a student movement to get HEIs to review their internal activities to reduce the impact on the environment, for example divesting from fossil fuels or implementing green offices. The idea of this event is to make international students aware of the impacts of a university on the climate (e.g. energy use, building materials, curricula, conference travels, canteen, waste system, etc.) and how that could be changed.

The workshop could first highlight the need for action by showing some statistics of the university. An expert from Climate Student Movement could, for example, introduce the idea of the different campaigns of their members and what a whole-institution approach is when getting a HEI to change their climate strategy - that not only climate change should be more present in curricula but that also all activities of the HEI as an institution are scrutinised. In the end, participants should reflect on what they would demand from their HEI and what could be improved.

Target group

International students who stay long enough to start a campaign.

External collaboration

- [Climate Student Movement](#);
- [FFF Climate Education](#);
- [SOS International](#);
- If available: green office at local HEI. Learn more about the [Green Offices movement](#) here;
- Environmental (student) associations.

Environmental considerations

Organisers could map the environmental impacts that a university has to be sure to consider all environmental impacts. HEIs run the risk of not taking a whole-institution approach and only focusing on energy or emissions and efforts by students should focus on highlighting a HEI's holistic and total impact on the environment. This can be the environmental footprint, but also includes the [environmental handprint](#), which relates to the positive impact on the environment (e.g. by educating students on environmental issues across education programmes or using renewable energy).

Examples

Check out [this Group in Sweden](#) that works to get their HEI to act on the climate crisis. They are members of the Climate Student Movement.

Volunteering on Exchange

Creative Preparation for Local Activism

Objective

Can be any of the topics of this guide and even beyond, depending on the local context.

Learning outcome for the participants

- Engaging with local activist groups and national or local environmental issues through crafting signs for activist demonstrations;
- Learning how to find a good strategy and the objectives behind an image or a slogan on a sign, so it communicates an impactful and understandable message. One good reference is the book “Image Politics” by Kevin Michael DeLuca.

Learning outcome for the organisers

They will benefit from participants’ ideas and creativity materialised in the signs.

Time allocation

One to five hours.

Description

In any Erasmus place, there will be local groups who organise political activities around local, national or international topics related to the environment. This is a chance for international students to engage with the local community and learn more about the exact issues they face

and prioritise. In collaboration with local groups, students can learn how to frame powerful and impactful messages through images, slogans, photos or drawings is vital for activism. This activity could have a prior space of brainstorming between organisers and participants to find the most impactful phrases and graphics they can put on the signs. It can also help internationals to learn the local language.

Then, the hand-crafting workshop(s) can be developed in open spaces like parks in order to avoid spills of paint or headaches provoked by sprays or gloss paint. It is important to consider the number of people attending the demonstrations, so participants will craft enough signs without wasting time and materials.

Target group

- Young local and international activists;
- School and university students;
- External volunteers from other associations.

External collaboration

- Local or regional authorities to authorise the use of public space;
- Local activist groups;
- Local hubs for civil society.

Environmental considerations

- It is very important to use recycled materials (carton, paper, wood sticks), ecological sprays, and water-based paint;
- After the hand-crafting workshop be sure to gather all the remaining materials and not let any trash on the floor.

Tips

It would be nice to craft these signs in partnership with local schools and universities as an assignment for students. Activists can count on more hands helping them and students will maybe pass a subject (according to the partnership) and have fun.

Experience a Self-Managed Community

Objectives

Fostering responsible consumption, fostering a circular economy.

Learning outcome for the participants

- Discovering new sustainable ways of living;
- Getting to know about agriculture, circular economy and disruptive self-sustained ways of co-living (could be a village or maybe a self-managed farm).

Learning outcome for the organisers

Establishing contact with a local community, organise and coordinate a group of young volunteers.

Time allocation

Two to three hours.

Description

In many places in the world, there are people who already try to live alternative lifestyles more in line with the planetary boundaries, and who constructively try to propose and live solutions for environmental issues. Many of them try to de-commercialise food or housing or live in alternative economic or democratic structures (e.g. how to deal with money or how to make decisions as a group).

Through this activity, international students get to experience local culture by engaging in volunteering activities in local communities while learning about alternative ways of living.

Target group

International students who are interested in getting to know the local culture and have some time to spare to volunteer.

External collaboration

Local activist groups, local communities and cooperatives (e.g. food cooperatives), local zero waste hubs, cultural centres.

Environmental considerations

Sometimes these communities are not that close to big cities, local research shall be made to find these spots and see how they can be reached by sustainable means of transport.

Tips

Many of these communities have been built over years and are often shaped by visions for a more socially just and inclusive society. This means in these spaces, people may pay more attention to pronouns and accessibility, they may be more sensitive to sexism, homophobia, classism, racism, etc. Organisers should make sure to communicate the rules/code of conduct of the place they are visiting to the volunteers beforehand and emphasise that even if you are volunteering you are a guest in a space with a story and philosophy which might require a certain openness and self-reflectiveness.

Examples

- In Valencia (ES) there is an [urban farm](#) where the neighbours manage the garden on their own, they each have a spot to cultivate and also have common grounds;
- In Enschede (NL), there is a place called [Tankstation](#), a cross-culture public space with a “give and take” shop, vegetarian and vegan food nights and art performances.

RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION

In this section, different activities are proposed to address the topics of a circular economy for different materials such as food, clothing, hygiene, and beauty products.

FABALISH

Aquafaba
Vegan Tzatziki
Sauce & Dip

Plant-based, organic, and Greek; in taste
with freshly cut cucumber, mint & oil
8 FL. OZ. (237 ML.)

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Events

Eco-City Tour

Objectives

Fostering responsible consumption, fostering a circular economy.

Learning outcome for the participants

- Discovering the city from a new perspective by getting to know places and shops promoting responsible consumption, while also getting in touch with the local communities;
- Learning more about responsible consumption.

Learning outcome for the organisers

- Getting to know the city from a different perspective;
- Building collaborations with local shops;
- Discovering places and products to improve responsible consumption.

Time allocation

From two to five hours.

Description

An international student who just arrived in a city could benefit from discovering all the different places, restaurants, and shops that promote responsible consumption. An eco-city tour is a perfect opportunity to discover the city from a different perspective and learn how to consume responsibly during their stay.

Target group

International students who want to learn more about ways to consume responsibly in the city they are living in.

External collaboration

- Local stores, restaurants, and services that promote responsible consumption;
- Local associations promoting responsible consumption that could help guide or designing the itinerary of the city rally.

Environmental considerations

- Use public/low-carbon transportation to travel in the city if necessary;
- Reduce the waste produced during the tour by e.g. bringing reusable boxes and bags in case you want to buy anything during this tour.

Tips

- Make the event more interactive and educational by including little games to play, quizzes to do, etc. about responsible consumption throughout the walk. A game at each checkpoint in the tour could be a good way to make the whole itinerary engaging and fun;
- Collaborate with an eco-friendly restaurant and provide discounts for lunch;
- Incorporate the different destinations of the Eco-City tour in any city tour you do and include other kinds of places to normalise thinking about sustainability at all times;
- Examples of places to look for: restaurants, zero-waste and bulk products shops, second-hand stores (clothes, furniture, etc.), ethical and local products shops, bike rental shops (or any shops that promote collaborative consumption), etc.

Examples

Several ESN sections have organised similar events in the past ([Thrift Shop Tour - consume with awareness](#), [Zero Waste Tour](#) or [Second-hand bookstore tour](#)).

Second-hand Fair

Objective

Fostering a circular economy.

Learning outcome for the participants

- Appreciating second-hand objects;
- Realising that second-hand doesn't mean low quality, and it even gives us so many more choices.

Learning outcome for the organisers

- Organising the logistics of a second-hand fair (location, cash, getting second-hand things);
- Promoting a circular economy and no-waste mentality as a great chance to find unique and low-cost objects.

Time allocation

A few hours in the afternoon, depending on the number of items to sell. It can also take place for a whole weekend.

Description

We all know the situation of having old clothes at home that are still in perfect condition, but we have grown out of them, just don't like them anymore, or they don't fit our current style. What to do when you are not ready to throw them? At a second-hand fair, they might find a new owner who was just looking for exactly this piece, and the other way around, you might just find a perfect new piece for yourself. Let's slow down the fast-fashion trend and bring back handing over old (but still in good condition!) things.

Target group

International students who just arrived in their exchange city and need new things, as well as international students about to leave the city who want to give away their things. International

students who want to reduce their consumption in general or who might not have the budget to buy new. Vintage lovers.

External collaboration

For this event, a collaboration could be done with local helping associations and charity shops that can receive items that haven't been sold or maybe even connect for sources to second-hand items to be sold during the fair.

Environmental considerations

Ensure low carbon reachability of the location. It should be reachable on foot, by bike or by public transport.

Tips

Have enough cash to give back change. Consider having a mirror at the place. Organise enough space to properly display available items to purchase.

Examples

ESN Roma LUISS organised a [Clothes Swapping Party](#) and ESN Saarbrücken hosted a [Colourful Upcycling Event](#). You can also check out the [Vintage Pop-Up Market](#) organised by ESN Bergamo or the [Second-hand Clothing Sale](#) by ESN Leiden.

Workshops

Cook for the Earth

Objectives

Fostering responsible consumption, encouraging slow food.

Learning outcome for the participants

Cooking sustainable meals with local and seasonal ingredients. Gaining awareness of seasonality in food resources as well as their environmental impact (e.g. carbon dioxide emissions, water resources as well as working conditions).

Learning outcome for the organisers

- Organising the space, tools and ingredients necessary to hold a cooking event;
- Choosing the right seasonal and local ingredients for delicious meals;
- Managing the participants to create a comfortable environment while managing to cook successfully.

Time allocation

The duration of a dinner (cooking for 1-2 hours + time to spend together afterwards to eat and relax).

Description

Cooking is one of the most efficient ways of bringing people together, and eating is a necessity for everyone! Eating delicious and good quality food is a big topic in most societies. Combining the social part of creating something together and sharing it afterwards whilst raising awareness of the social and environmental impact that we have on the earth by choosing the right ingredients for our meal is a logical step. Cooking for the earth can focus on reducing carbon dioxide emissions

by cutting down meat consumption as well as avoiding imported and far-transported products, choosing local organic or fair trade ingredients that have low water consumption, as well as being aware of the working conditions of humans and animals involved in harvesting and producing processes or the environmental consequences of monocultures and mass production.

Target group

International students who love or would like to learn how to cook. Slow food lovers and students who love good food in general. Students interested in environmental sustainability.

External collaboration

- Local shops and farmers for local and seasonal food;
- Local cooking schools for experts to hold the workshop or help prepare it;
- Fair trade shops;
- Local associations or NGOs promoting responsible consumption.

Environmental considerations

- Choose local and seasonal produce for the workshop to keep the carbon footprint low;
- Consider cooking meatless;
- Pay attention to purchase unpackaged products where possible to reduce waste;
- Assess the number of participants ahead and make registration obligatory in order to reduce waste;
- Be consistent in choosing the ingredients (organic, fair trade, local, etc.) and make sure to know the whole process of the products arriving to your plate.

Tips

- Vegan meals would be the preferred scenario, but also consider that people can be led to understanding in small steps, and it might be worth to offer non-vegan, but still conscious alternatives.
- Ask for a partial payment beforehand to avoid last-minute cancellations
- Ask about and prepare for any food intolerances or allergies as well as food preferences - think about using the learning outcome to organise follow-up events combining them with fun or cultural elements such as a [Conscious Running Dinner](#), [Sustainable International Dinners](#), a Vegan Blind Date or Seasonal Dinner in the Dark.

Examples

ESN Trento organised a Workshop called [Your Dinner Makes a Difference](#) and ESN Iasi hosted a [Zero Waste Dinner](#) discussing the impact our food has on the environment.

For dinners afterwards check out the following activities: ESN Leiden hosted a [Cultural Dish Made Vegan](#) as well as a [Vegan Cooking Class](#) or [Green Kitchen Dinner](#). ESN Trabzon organised this [Vegan Pic-nic](#). You can also check out ESN Ege Universities [Veganuary Dinner](#). Why not combine it with some [Leftover Recipes](#) to avoid waste as did ESN Iasi?

Make Your Own Hygiene Products and Cosmetics

Objectives

Fostering a circular economy, fostering responsible consumption.

Learning outcome for the participants

- Understanding the environmental impact of commercial hygiene products and cosmetics;
- Learning how to make hygiene products and cosmetics.

Learning outcome for the organisers

- Acquiring the knowledge to make hygiene products and cosmetics from scratch and pass on the knowledge to the participants.

Time allocation

From two hours on, depending on the specificities of the workshop.

Description

The environmental impact of commercial hygiene products and cosmetics is terrifying. This industry generates immense amounts of plastic and air pollution, poisons our oceans with toxic chemicals and irresponsibly drains nature's resources. Fortunately, one can still decide to bypass those industries and make their own sustainable products in the comfort of their home. This hands-on activity will allow you to explore the simple but effective ways of making your own panoply of cleaning, hygiene products and cosmetics.

Target group

Anyone wanting to learn more about the environmental impact of hygiene and cosmetics industries and wanting to adopt more sustainable products.

External collaboration

- Local associations, stores and herbal shops specialising in sustainable products that could provide their expertise and the ingredients required for the workshop;
- Researchers from the universities' biology and/or chemistry departments that would provide their expertise for the workshop.

Environmental considerations

- Use jars and containers that people already have, and when these options are not available, propose sustainable packaging (reusable, biodegradable, recyclable, etc...);
- Make sure that the ingredients used throughout the activity are sourced responsibly, if possible locally, and are grown or produced in an environmentally-friendly manner;
- Have a clear idea of what you want to produce to avoid waste;
- Indicate the exact material and quantities required for the workshop to avoid waste.

Tips

- To know more about the environmental impact of the cosmetics industry, you can check out this well-sourced [article](#) by Treehugger.
- Some sources of inspiration for recipes include
 - » [Homemade makeup recipes](#) by the Treehugger;
 - » [Sustainable cleaning products](#) by the Earth.fm;
 - » [Resources for DIY cosmetics](#) by the Considerate Consumer;
 - » And countless other articles and videos you can easily find by searching on the Internet!
- Try and test the recipes before the event to make sure of the quantities and the final output.

Examples

- Some ESN sections already organised activities to create their own hygiene and beauty products, including
 - » [DIY Natural Cosmetics Workshop with ESN](#), by ESN Uni Wien;
 - » [Homemade Beauty Products with ESN-EYE](#), by ESN-EYE Lodz.
- You can choose to couple a DIY cosmetics activity with a sustainable night-out or fashion show to showcase how to adopt a sustainable beauty and fashion lifestyle from A to Z.

Repair Lab

Objective

Fostering a circular economy.

Learning outcome for the participants

Acquiring concrete repairing skills as well as awareness to give a second life to used objects.

Learning outcome for the organisers

- Learning how to organise the necessary space and tools for a repair lab;
- Acquiring concrete repairing skills;
- Managing and supporting participants in achieving their goals.

Time allocation

Half a day, where participants can join and leave whenever it fits for them.

Description

Many of us have things at home that have not stopped functioning the way they should or don't look good anymore but are still too good to throw out. Why not give them a second life? Organise a space and necessary tools to repair e.g. bikes, furniture or electronic devices. Everyone brings what they want to repair or upcycle. Together with experts and with joint effort, those objects can be given a second life.

Target group

(International) students who like to get hands-on and want to repair things, want to reduce waste, or live on a budget.

External collaboration

Local garages and shops can help to provide the necessary tools and parts as well as helpful knowledge.

Environmental considerations

When parts or whole devices/ pieces are beyond repair, pay attention to the correct disposal:

- for batteries and other technical devices or parts, be careful and prevent health damages that might occur when handling them;
- and dispose them in the correct containers, appropriate facilities or call a company to collect them (different actions might apply to different countries);
- consider the carbon footprint in the reachability of the location. The best would be to reach it carbon-free (by foot or bike) or by public transportation.

Tips

- If costs incur, ask for a small participation fee or deposit beforehand to avoid last-minute cancellations.
- Advise the participants to come in comfortable and ok-to-get-dirty and ripped clothing. Repairing things might be dirty work.

Examples

ESN Granada organised a [Customise Your Clothes](#) event. Take inspiration from the [Reduce, reuse, recycle! challenge](#) by ESN GEG Genova.

Other ideas could be to repair bikes, technological device repairing or upcycling clothes or furniture.

'Veganise' Your Favourite Recipe

Objective

Fostering responsible consumption.

Learning outcome for the participants

- Gaining awareness of the diverse range of vegan food while getting to know dishes from all around the world;
- Learning to be creative and open-minded to find new ways of adapting loved recipes and finding the local resources needed to cook the dishes;
- Getting to know new dishes and improving cooking skills;
- Becoming aware of the environmental aspects of meat consumption such as the CO₂ emissions, high water usage, and waste creation by animal farms and fishing.

Learning outcome for the organisers

- Learning how to coordinate and create a campaign, establish partnerships with local stores and passing on the message of delicious vegan options without seeming too educational or persuasive;
- Getting to know new ideas and options;
- Learning how to raise awareness about environmental aspects of reducing meat consumption such as the reduction of CO₂ emissions, water usage and waste created by animal farms as well as the suffering of the animals;

Time allocation

The campaign can run for several weeks, depending on the participants. The more recipes are received, the longer the campaign can run.

Description

Sharing International recipes is one of the most present aspects about intercultural exchange, showing us that food and cooking bring people together and most people are passionate about it. Organisers will develop an online campaign encouraging local and international students to share

vegan versions of their traditional dishes that they will cook themselves, and possibly eat, in a closing event. Presenting the vegan versions of participants' favourite dishes from all around the world will showcase the vast range of options possible to cook vegan. It gives ideas that people might be clueless about, and makes them want to try what they see. The idea is to share a design template for the recipe with photos, with which the participants can then recreate and share their favourite veganised dishes. Those can be published on social media (and in a competition even be chosen as the best recipe and awarded a prize).

To bring it further, a cookbook with different dishes from around the world - but in vegan - can be published. As a side effect, the environmentalist aspects of high meat consumption could be addressed. By reducing or cutting out meat from our diets, we can contribute to lowering CO2 emissions, huge waste masses and high water consumption, especially in the dairy and cattle industries but also the poultry industry. Harmful consequences such as climate change and the extinction of countless species are caused by rainforest clearings, the destruction of coral reefs and sea vegetation as well as overfishing done by the meat and fishing industry.

Target group

International students interested in sharing vegan cooking ideas with local and international students and eating delicious dishes together.

External collaboration

Food being at the centre of this campaign, collaborations with local food stores or food savings organisations would be ideal.

Environmental considerations

- Raise awareness for local and seasonal ingredients to be used in the dishes;
- Focus on online promotion:
 - » If it should be printed material (e.g. in a cooking book), analyse where to print in the most sustainable way (company, the paper used, etc.);
 - » analyse the need for printed media and only act accordingly to save resources.

Tips

- For a successful campaign, a good designer might be needed.
- Define the concrete frame for the campaign: is it going to be a social media campaign or a printed book? How extensive should it be?
- Consider integrating a contest with a prize to motivate people to participate.

Examples

ESN Leiden executed a [Meatless Monday Social Media Campaign](#), which follows a similar idea. You can also take inspiration from [Healthy and Sustainable Recipe + Cooking Contest](#) of ESN Roma LUISS (not vegan version) or ESN UE Poznans [Vege Day](#).

Campaigns

The ABC of Responsible Consumption

Objective

Fostering a circular economy.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning how to consume responsibly in their city/country and adopt more sustainable habits.

Learning outcome for the organisers

- Learning how to coordinate and create a campaign;
- Establishing partnerships with local stores and associations;
- Gaining insights into the different options available to consume more responsibly.

Time allocation

One week.

Description

There's an increasing urge to adopt more sustainable, more environmentally-aware lifestyles. These include a shift towards responsible consumption. It applies to a plethora of domains, such as food, clothing and furniture to name a few. Anyone could adapt their habits, one step at a time.

This campaign will show how easy it is to adopt a more responsible lifestyle, while exploring what the local community has to offer in each of its facets, from second-hand stores to zero-waste and bulk shops.

Target group

Anyone interested in getting to know more about responsible consumption and would like to adopt a more sustainable lifestyle.

External collaboration

- Local associations that promote responsible consumption that could help with the content of the campaign;
- Local municipalities;
- Local stores that sell ethical, responsible products.

Environmental considerations

Focus on online promotion and assess the needs for printed material (posters...).

Tips

- Always provide sources for any information you share.
- Diversify the content of the campaign. The potential topics could be: food, clothing, cosmetics, plastic, transport/travel, energy efficiency, reuse & repair...
- Examples of guidelines to help shape up the content of the campaign:
 - » A guideline for sustainable consumption in Bern [Out and about sustainably in Bern](#), by the University of Bern;
 - » [Sustainable Consumption Guide](#), by the University of Oxford.
- Search for already existing resources on sustainable consumption in your city to include in your campaign!
- Combine the campaign with a contest to incentivise the adoption of sustainable and responsible ways of consumption (see Green Lifestyle contest below).

Examples

Many ESN sections have developed online campaigns related to responsible consumption. You can check out the following ones:

- [Make Your Student Life Greener](#), by ESN Roma LUISS;
- [Zero Waste 101](#), by ESN BelUPgrade.

Green Lifestyle Contest

Objectives

Fostering a circular economy, fostering responsible consumption.

Learning outcome for the participants

- Learning how to consume responsibly in their city/country;
- Understanding how to adopt more sustainable habits.

Learning outcome for the organisers

- Learning how to coordinate and create a campaign;
- Establishing partnerships with local stores and associations;
- Gaining insights into the different options available to consume more responsibly.

Time allocation

One week up to one month (depending on how organisers want to spread the challenges out).

Description

Our consumption behaviour has a direct impact on climate change and is one of the causes of the collapse of biodiversity. To start renewing our relationship with the environment, we need to reconsider our consumption habits, and incorporate more responsible and circular choices. This contest will incentivise the adoption of more sustainable habits and enable international students to explore different opportunities in their area. They compete against fellow participants in a series of challenges and a prize awaits the winner(s).

Target group

Anyone interested in getting to know more about responsible consumption and wanting to adopt a more sustainable lifestyle.

External collaboration

- Local associations that could help with the creation of challenges and the promotion of the campaign;
- Local universities that could support in the promotion of the campaign and the choice of the prizes;
- Local stores and restaurants that could propose prizes for the contest.

Environmental considerations

Make sure that the prizes are in line with the goal of the contest.

Tips

- Always provide sources for any information you share.
- Make sure the actions in your challenges are quantifiable.
- Diversify the content of the campaign. The potential topics could be food, clothing, cosmetics, plastic, transport/travel, energy efficiency, reuse & repair...

Examples

One could draw inspiration from already existing contests, such as the [Project Green Challenge](#), or the [Green Challenges](#) of ESN Greece.

Volunteering on Exchange

Vegetable Garden

Objectives

Fostering a circular economy, encouraging slow food.

Learning outcome for the participants

Learning how to grow their own food from sowing, taking care and harvesting.

Learning outcome for the organisers

- Organising time and resources to ensure constant care of the plants, how to grow our own food from sowing, taking care and harvesting,;
- Establishing collaborations with local shops and farmers in order to get the land and tools to work with.

Time allocation

It can be a continuous project - try to keep things running for the whole year.

Description

Especially after the pandemic, plant care has become an obsession of many. One part of conscious consumption is growing one's own food. Vegetables are especially easy to grow on your balcony or garden and some even in flats. But not everyone has the space or thus time to care for a little vegetable garden. The solution is to share the load. Organise a piece of land as well as the necessary tools and decide together, which vegetables, herbs and fruits to plant. Organise the planting, watering and harvesting as well as other necessary tasks. Some knowledge-sharing sessions or workshops can take place to support the success of this project. After the harvesting,

the food may be equally distributed or a joint cooking event with the self-grown vegetables can take place. In this way, your international students will experience directly how to be more sustainable in some of their most important daily life choices.

Target group

International students who are interested in gardening, plants, local and seasonal food or healthy cooking.

External collaboration

- Local garden centre for tools and plants/seeds;
- University, municipality or other institutions to grant the grounds;
- Local farmers for knowledge/ground or workshops;
- Other local associations or NGOs interested in responsible consumption.

Environmental considerations

Choose domestic plants to plant.

Tips

- Have necessary tools handy: shovel, pruning scissors, hose, buckets, wheelbarrow, fertiliser, earth, etc.
- Schedule enough capacities to take care of the plants through their whole circle.
- Think about plans for when the vegetables will be harvested - Cook for the Earth / Green BBQ.
- Experiment with vegan dishes.
- To better promote the event, you can do a social media campaign on the impact of food, maybe in an interactive way.
- Promote the event to the whole local community and try to involve several associations and institutions.
- After the activity, ask the participants for feedback on the messages conveyed by the event and make them reflect on such issues.

Examples

- Check out ESN Granadas [Urban Garden](#) event or ESN Chieti Pescara's [Gardening Contest Meeting](#). You can also take inspiration from ESN Lisbon's [Farmer For A Day](#) event.
- University or community vegetable and fruit garden.
- Similar alternative: community beehive.
- You can also teach online how to create a [Micro Garden in Your Flat](#) as did ESN Iasi.

The background features a complex geometric pattern of overlapping lines in various shades of green and white. The lines intersect to form a series of triangles and polygons of different sizes and orientations. The colors range from a deep forest green to a bright, vibrant lime green, with white lines providing a high-contrast structure.

GLOSSARY

Biodiversity

Biodiversity, also called biological diversity, is the variety of life found in a place on Earth or, often, the total variety of life on Earth. A common measure of this variety, called species richness, is the count of species in an area. Biodiversity also encompasses the genetic variety within each species and the variety of ecosystems that species create.

Source: [Britannica](#)

Body of water

The part of the earth's surface covered with water (such as a river or lake, or ocean).

Source: [The Free Dictionary](#)

Botanical garden

A garden often with greenhouses for the culture, study, and exhibition of special plants.

Source: [Merriam-Webster](#)

Carbon footprint

Amount of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions associated with all the activities of a person or other entity (e.g., building, corporation, country, etc.). It includes direct emissions, such as those that result from fossil-fuel combustion in manufacturing, heating, and transportation, as well as emissions required to produce the electricity associated with goods and services consumed. In addition, the carbon footprint concept also often includes the emissions of other greenhouse gases, such as methane, nitrous oxide, or chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs).

Source: [Britannica](#)

Carbon-free

Either no usage of fossil fuels or no emission of carbon-containing greenhouse gases. For example, a state is carbon-free if all of its electricity is from clean energy sources like wind, solar, and nuclear.

Source: [Carbon-Free Glossary](#)

Circular economy

Many authors define circular economy with a strong focus on how material resources are managed. According to Hislop and Hill (2011), "The circular economy represents a development strategy that maximises resource efficiency and minimises waste production, within the context of sustainable economic and social development". For Preston (2012) "A circular economy is an approach that would transform the function of resources in the economy. Waste from factories would become a valuable input to another process—and products could be repaired, reused or upgraded instead of thrown away." If waste and resources are central aspects of the concept, the definitions aim at clarifying that circular economy goes beyond conventional waste management principles. "A circular economy goes beyond the pursuit of waste prevention and waste reduction to inspire technological, organisational, and social innovation throughout the value chain in order to 'design -out' waste from the beginning, rather than relying solely on waste recycling at the end of the chain".

Source: [\(Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013\) - Circular Academy](#)

Compostable and non-compostable waste

Compostable waste means any organic waste materials that are source separated for processing or composting, such as yard waste and food waste. Non-compostable means incapable of decomposing naturally or of yielding safe, non-toxic end products, after decomposition.

Source: [Law Insider](#)

Composting

Composting is the natural process of recycling organic matter, such as leaves and food scraps, into a valuable fertiliser that can enrich soil and plants. Anything that grows decomposes eventually; composting simply speeds up the process by providing an ideal environment for bacteria, fungi, and other decomposing organisms (such as worms, sow bugs, and nematodes) to do their work. The resulting decomposed matter, which often ends up looking like fertile garden soil, is called compost. Fondly referred to by farmers as “black gold,” compost is rich in nutrients and can be used for gardening, horticulture, and agriculture.

Source: [Natural Resources Defence Council](#)

Eco-educational

An emphasis on the inescapable embeddedness of human beings in natural settings and the responsibilities that arise from this relationship. Rather than seeing nature as other—a set of phenomena capable of being manipulated like parts of a machine—the practice of ecological education requires viewing human beings as one part of the natural world and human cultures as an outgrowth of interactions between our species and particular places.

Source: [Cambridge](#)

Ecosystem

The complex of living organisms, their physical environment, and all their interrelationships in a particular space unit. An ecosystem can be categorised into its abiotic constituents, including minerals, climate, soil, water, sunlight, and all other non-living elements, and its biotic constituents, consisting of all its living members. Linking these constituents together are two major forces: the flow of energy through the ecosystem and the cycling of nutrients within the ecosystem. Ecosystems vary in size: some are small enough to be contained within single water droplets, while others are large enough to encompass entire landscapes and regions.

Source: [Britannica](#)

Eco-tourism

The responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment, sustains the well-being of the local people, and involves interpretation and education.

Source: [The International Ecotourism Society](#)

Ethology

The study of animal behaviour. Ethology is a combination of laboratory and field science, with strong ties to certain other disciplines—e.g., neuroanatomy, ecology, evolution. The ethologist is interested in the behavioural process rather than in a particular animal group and often studies one type of behaviour (e.g., aggression) in a number of unrelated animals.

Source: [Britannica](#)

Emissions

The act of sending gas, heat, light, etc. out into the air. - Cambridge. In particular, the greenhouse gases emission into the earth's atmosphere, like carbon dioxide, contribute to the greenhouse effect.

Source: [Collins](#)

Endangered species

An endangered species is a type of organism (it can be an animal, a tree, a coral, a fungus, an insect etc) that is threatened by extinction. Species become endangered for two main reasons: loss of habitat and loss of genetic variation. The [International Union for Conservation of Nature's Red List of Threatened Species](#) classifies species at high risk of global extinction.

Source: [WWF](#), [National Geographic](#), [IUCN](#)

Fauna

All the animals living in a particular area, time period, or environment.

Source: [The Britannica Dictionary](#)

Flora

All the plants living in a particular area, time period, or environment.

Source: [The Britannica Dictionary](#)

Green (urban) areas/spaces

Areas with vegetation within or partly embraced by urban fabric. This class is assigned to urban greenery, which usually has recreational or ornamental character and is usually accessible to the public. [Copernicus](#), the European programme for monitoring the Earth, provides a list of possible places under this category.

Source: [Copernicus](#)

Horticulture

Horticulture is the science and art of the development, sustainable production, marketing and use of high-value, intensively cultivated food and ornamental plants. Horticultural crops are diverse, including: Annual and perennial species, Fruits and vegetables, Decorative indoor plants and landscape plants.

Source: [Michigan State University](#)

Low-carbon

Causing only a relatively small amount of carbon dioxide to be released into the atmosphere. According to [ACER](#), low-carbon gases, such as biogas, bio methane, or hydrogen produced via electrolysis by using renewable-generated electricity (from wind, solar, etc.), are important contributors for transitioning towards a less fossil fuel dependent and, ultimately, carbon-neutral energy sector.

Source: [oxfordlearnersdictionaries](#), [acer.europa.eu](#)

Native species

Native species means, with respect to a particular ecosystem, a species that, other than as a result of an introduction, historically occurred or currently occurs in that ecosystem.

Source: [Law Insider](#)

Natural reserve

A nature reserve is a part of the territory where the preservation of the fauna, flora, soil, water, mineral and fossil deposits and, in general, of the natural environment is of particular importance. No artificial intervention likely to degrade such a territory should be allowed in it.

Source: [INSEE](#)

NGO

The term non-governmental organisation (NGO) is very broad and encompasses many different types of organisations. They include international charities, research institutes, churches, community-based organisations, lobby groups and professional associations. Traditionally, NGOs are value-based organisations that depend, completely or in part, on charitable donations and voluntary service. The United Nations (U.N.) Department of Public Information (DPI) defines the NGO as “a not-for profit, voluntary citizen’s group that is organised on a local, national or international level to address issues in support of the public good. Task-oriented and made up of people with a common interest, NGOs perform a variety of services and humanitarian functions, bring citizen’s concerns to Governments, monitor policy and program implementation, and encourage participation of civil society stakeholders at the community level.”

Source: [APA](#)

Organic

(of food, farming methods, etc.) produced or practised without using artificial chemicals.

Source: [oxfordlearnersdictionaries](#)

Organic materials

Organic material means any chemical compound of carbon including diluents and thinners which are liquids at standard conditions and which are used as solvents, viscosity reducers, or cleaning agents, but excluding methane, acetone, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, carbonic acid, metallic carbonic acid, metallic carbide, metallic carbonates, and ammonium carbonate.

Source: [Law Insider](#)

Protected area

A protected area is a clearly defined geographical space that is recognised as and dedicated to achieving the long-term conservation of nature – with its associated ecosystem services and cultural values – and is managed, through legal or other effective means, to do so. This is the essence of the definition provided by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). Protected areas encompass a wide variety of natural and semi-natural environments. Historically, they have taken many forms, from indigenous communities’ sacred sites and medieval hunting reserves, to more modern national parks and nature reserves. These different forms reflected the different needs that these areas were created to serve.

Source: [European Environment Agency](#)

Recycle

To sort and collect rubbish in order to treat it and produce useful materials that can be used again. According to [EPA](#), recycling is the process of collecting and processing materials that would otherwise be thrown away as trash and turning them into new products. Recycling can benefit your community and the environment.

Source: [Cambridge Dictionary](#), [EPA](#)

Responsible consumption

[Sustainable consumption and production](#) is about doing more and better with less. It is also about decoupling economic growth from environmental degradation, increasing resource efficiency and promoting sustainable lifestyles. Sustainable consumption and production can also contribute substantially to poverty alleviation and the transition towards low-carbon and green economies.

Source: [UN.org](#)

Seed bomb

Seed bombs are an ancient Japanese practice called Tsuchi Dango, meaning 'Earth Dumpling' (seed bombs are made from clay earth). Seed bombs were reintroduced in 1938 by a Japanese microbiologist/ farmer Masanobu Fukuoka (1913–2008). A seed bomb is a seed that has been wrapped in soil materials, usually a mixture of clay and compost, and then dried... . Seed balls are an easy and sustainable way to cultivate plants in a way that provides a larger window of time when the sowing can occur. They also are a convenient dispersal mechanism for guerrilla gardeners and people with achy backs.

Source: [seedbomb.ie](#) & [seed-balls.com](#)

Slow food

Slow Food is a global, grassroots organisation, founded in 1989 to prevent the disappearance of local food cultures and traditions, counteract the rise of fast life and combat people's dwindling interest in the food they eat, where it comes from and how our food choices affect the world around us.

Source: [SlowFood.com](#)

Slow tourism / Slow travel

Slow tourism is an emerging tourism trend, which serves as an antidote to some of the negative aspects of mass tourism. At the same time, slow tourism places a strong emphasis on sustainability, engagement with local culture, and fully appreciating travel experiences.

Source: [Revfine](#)

Sustainable tourism

Areas with vegetation within or partly embraced by urban fabric. This class is assigned to urban greenery, which usually has recreational or ornamental character and is usually accessible to the public. [Copernicus](#), the European programme for monitoring the Earth, provides a list of possible places under this category.

Source: [GlobalDevelopmentResearchCenter](#)

Urban areas

An urban area or a “big urban area” is a group of touching municipalities, without pockets of clear land, encompassing an urban centre (urban unit) providing at least 10 000 jobs, and by rural districts or urban units (urban periphery) among which at least 40 % of employed resident population works in the centre or in the municipalities attracted by this centre.

Source: [INSEE](#)

Urban nature

Urban Nature can be understood as areas in urban environments that are home to plants and non-human animals. Urban nature is not just dedicated recreational space such as public parks, but other types of informal green spaces, for example, green streetscapes, nature areas, roof gardens and community gardens.

Source: [Natureforall](#)

Veganism

Veganism is a philosophy and way of living which seeks to exclude—as far as is possible and practicable—all forms of exploitation of, and cruelty to, animals for food, clothing or any other purpose; and by extension, promotes the development and use of animal-free alternatives for the benefit of animals, humans and the environment.

Source: [VeganSociety](#)

Vegetarianism

The theory or practice of living solely upon [vegetables](#), [fruits](#), [grains](#), [legumes](#), and [nuts](#)—with or without the addition of [milk](#) products and [eggs](#)—generally for [ethical](#), [ascetic](#), environmental, or nutritional reasons. All forms of flesh (meat, fowl, and [seafood](#)) are excluded from all vegetarian diets, but many vegetarians use milk and milk products.

Source: [Britannica](#)

Vegetation

Plants in general: plants that cover a particular area.

Source: [Britannica](#)

Waste

Waste (or refuse) is non-hazardous solid waste that requires collection and transport to a processing or disposal site. Refuse includes garbage and rubbish. Garbage is mostly decomposable food waste or yard waste that is highly putrescible, while rubbish is mostly dry material such as [glass](#), paper, cloth, or wood that does not readily [decompose](#).

Source: [Britannica](#)

Wildlife protection

Wildlife conservation is the practice of protecting plant and animal species and their habitats. As part of the world’s ecosystems, wildlife provides balance and stability to nature’s processes. The goal of wildlife conservation is to ensure the survival of these species, and to educate people on living sustainably with other species.

Source: [NationalGeographic](#)

Worm composting

Worm composting is using worms to recycle food scraps and other organic material into a valuable soil amendment called vermicompost, or worm compost. Worms eat food scraps, which become compost as they pass through the worm’s body. Compost exits the worm through its tail end.

Source: [CornellCompostinginSchools](#)

